

THE ROLE OF THE SOVIET UNION IN THE GENEVA CONFERENCE ON ENDING THE WAR AND RESTORING PEACE IN INDOCHINA, 1954

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Abstract

The 1954 Geneva Conference resulted from a fierce negotiation and struggle between forces representing the global peace movement and colonialism's efforts to maintain its control. The Soviet Union, as the stronghold of socialism and a flagbearer for national liberation movements worldwide, sided with the Democratic Republic of Vietnam and other Indochinese nations. Not only was it the initiator of the conference, the Soviet Union also played a leading role in preparing and designing the event as a "diplomatic front," persistently upholding the position of ending the war and restoring peace in Indochina. Thanks to its firm yet flexible and skillful leadership, the Geneva Conference achieved success and became a historic milestone for Vietnam. This triumph also significantly elevated the international standing of Vietnam, China, and the Indochinese countries.

Keywords: Geneva Conference, Diplomatic Relations, Soviet Union, Vietnam

1. INTRODUCTION

The Geneva Conference was a multilateral international gathering aimed at resolving critical issues arising from the Korean War and the First Indochina War, and alleviating global tensions. It was held from April 26 to July 21, 1954. The conference involved nine delegations (the United States, the United Kingdom, France, the Soviet Union, China, the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, the State of Vietnam [a member of the French Union], Cambodia, and Laos). Over 75 days, the conference featured eight plenary sessions and 23 restricted meetings, accompanied by intensive diplomatic exchanges, both open and clandestine.

As one of the great powers in attendance, the Soviet Union represented democratic and progressive international forces and played a key role in balancing the global power dynamics between the two superpowers of the time (the USSR and the United States). The Soviet delegation undertook a significant workload: conducting bilateral and multilateral engagements, preparing comprehensive information and materials, and shaping the negotiation script. The conference concluded with the signing of agreements to cease hostilities and restore peace in Indochina, abolishing French colonial rule and recognizing the independence of Vietnam, Laos, and Cambodia. Analyzing the Soviet Union's role in the Geneva Conference helps clarify its policy toward Indochina, especially Vietnam, and underscores its geopolitical standing about other powers such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and France during the Cold War.

2. OVERVIEW OF VIETNAM-SOVIET UNION DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS BEFORE THE 1954 GENEVA CONFERENCE

In early 1947, the Soviet Union publicly condemned the French colonial plan to extend and intensify the war in Indochina. Shortly thereafter, President Ho Chi Minh sent a letter to Stalin requesting that the Soviet Union bring the Franco-Vietnamese conflict before the United Nations General Assembly (Van, 2010). By 1949, following the victory of the Chinese revolution, the Democratic Republic of Vietnam

opened its borders and established connections with socialist countries, initiating relations with the Communist Party and government of the Soviet Union.

On January 1, 1950, President Ho Chi Minh issued a call for the establishment of diplomatic relations between Vietnam and other countries. His appeal became a significant issue on the agenda of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party of the Soviet Union. On January 30, 1950, the Central Committee passed a resolution to establish diplomatic relations between the Soviet Union and the Democratic Republic of Vietnam. This event became a focal point in international relations and "caused real anxiety and dismay among the French ruling authorities" (SRADV, 2019). Immediately afterward, the Soviet government undertook various measures to strengthen political and diplomatic ties with Vietnam.

In April 1950, the Soviet Union sent French-language books and newspapers, mobile film projectors, Soviet movies, propaganda materials, newspapers, and journals to Vietnam. The first shipment proposed by the Committee for Cultural Relations with Foreigners included: 43 French-language books, including Lenin's works, political and artistic publications; zinc photo plates of Soviet Party and government leaders; 500 issues of the journal *New Times* in French; a mobile film projector with eight films (dubbed in French and Russian); a gramophone and records; Soviet music and songbooks; a VEF radio receiver; and Young Pioneer accessories....

In August 1950, the Soviet Union sent congratulatory messages for the fifth anniversary of Vietnam's National Day, including letters from the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet to the President and the Foreign Minister of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam. The message to President Ho Chi Minh stated: "On behalf of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR and in my name, I extend my congratulations and best wishes to the people of Vietnam on the occasion of the National Day of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam" (SRADV, 2019)

On Vietnam's side, in February 1950, President Ho Chi Minh made an unofficial visit to the Soviet Union, where he met with high-ranking leaders including

Stalin, Malenkov, Molotov, Bulganin, and Khrushchev. The visit helped Soviet leaders gain a better understanding of Vietnam's revolution and resistance efforts. Bilateral cooperation began to expand. In May 1950, the Vietnam–Soviet Friendship Association was founded in the Viet Bac revolutionary base, with Ton Duc Thang as its president. The association soon established branches in various agencies, enterprises, military units, and localities. Its emergence spurred political and social activities linked to the Soviet Union throughout the Viet Bac base (Minh, 1995).

In February 1951, the 2nd National Congress of the Indochinese Communist Party (held in Viet Bac) declared that "the socialist Soviet Union and the newly democratic countries from Eastern Europe to East Asia form a vast bloc," "within which nations are united with a common purpose and free of contradictions," and "this bloc represents progress and a bright future for humanity." The congress emphasized that the Vietnamese revolution must "maintain close solidarity with the Soviet Union, China, and other people's democratic countries," "support colonial and semi-colonial liberation movements," and "expand people-to-people diplomacy, fostering friendly relations with any government that respects Vietnam's sovereignty, and establish diplomatic relations on principles of freedom, equality, and mutual benefit" (CPV, 1951). Following the congress, political, diplomatic, and cultural ties between Vietnam and the Soviet Union broadened significantly. In April 1951, a Vietnamese delegation attended the International Economic Conference in the Soviet Union. President Ho Chi Minh subsequently published articles about the USSR, such as "Vietnam in 1950 and 1951: The Beginning of the Liberation War and the Soviet Role in Establishing Democracy," discussing the Soviet Union's economic achievements and its Great Patriotic War (1941–1945). Meanwhile, the Soviet press—including Pravda, Izvestia, Red Star, Red Navy, Komsomolskaya Pravda, Trud, and New Times—stepped up its coverage of Vietnam. "These propaganda efforts not only played a crucial role in fostering friendship and cooperation between the two governments and peoples but also contributed significantly to raising Vietnam's international profile" (Van, 2010).

3. THE SOVIET UNION'S PROPOSAL AND DESIGN OF THE GENEVA NEGOTIATION CONFERENCE

Following World War II, the Soviet Union emerged victorious and became a cornerstone of the global revolutionary movement. With its immense prestige and influence, the Soviet Union became a rallying force for national liberation movements across Asia, Africa, and Latin America. To counter Soviet influence, the United States launched the Marshall Plan and formed the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (1949), along with several military alliances such as ANZUS (1951) in the Pacific, SEATO in Southeast Asia, and CENTO in the Middle East, aimed at containing socialism and undermining the progressive and peace movements.

In response to U.S. rearmament policies, in June 1951, the Soviet Union proposed that "the warring parties begin immediate negotiations to suspend hostilities

and sign an armistice agreement" in Korea, thereby promoting the resolution of international conflicts through negotiation (Giang, 1962). From 1953 onward, as U.S. intervention in Indochina deepened, the Soviet Union raised international awareness about "ceasefire in Korea and promoting an end to the Indochina War" (Patti, 1980). In August 1953, the Soviet Union sent a note to Britain, France, and the United States proposing a five-power conference (USSR, UK, France, US, China) to seek solutions for reducing tensions in the Far East. At the Berlin Conference (January 25 to February 18, 1954), the Soviet Union proposed a meeting of the foreign ministers of the USSR, US, UK, France, and China "to consider urgent measures for reducing tensions in international relations" (Giang, 1962). This proposal was not supported by the United States, which rejected the participation of the People's Republic of China. However, due to the Soviet Union's persistent efforts, the conference issued a joint communiqué agreeing "that the issue of restoring peace in Indochina would be addressed at a subsequent conference, and that representatives of the USSR, US, UK, France, the People's Republic of China, and other concerned nations would be invited to participate" (SRADV, 2019).

Following the Berlin Conference communiqué, during the plenary session of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union on March 2, 1954, the issues of Korea and the Indochina War became key agenda items. Soviet Foreign Minister Molotov delivered a presentation covering numerous issues related to international relations and peace negotiations aimed at resolving conflicts in Korea and the Indochina War. Regarding the Geneva Conference specifically, the presentation emphasized that it would be a conference "to restore peace in Indochina with the participation of all countries involved in the matter." Molotov's speech also affirmed that "the complex task facing the Geneva Conference is to ensure the restoration of peace and the national rights of the people of Indochina. This will depend largely on the stance of the French Government and on the recognition by all participating delegates of the necessity to resolve the issue of peace in Indochina not using continuing a senseless war, but through negotiations based on the principles of freedom and national independence for the peoples of Indochina" (SRADV, 2019).

After the plenary session of the Central Committee, the Soviet Union made extensive efforts to prepare for a multilateral international conference, anticipating significant challenges and complexities. The Soviet diplomatic corps actively carried out bilateral and multilateral contacts, while also intensively preparing information, documents, and materials for the conference under the guiding principle of "ensuring by all means that the Geneva Conference must take place" (Diep and Think, 2024). Numerous bilateral meetings and the exchange of diplomatic notes took place, articulating the views and positions between the Soviet Union and other relevant parties. For instance, on March 5, 1954, the Soviet Ambassador to the People's Republic of China met with the Ambassador of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam to discuss developments in the Viet-

namese resistance war, the Vietnamese Workers' Party's understanding of the Geneva Conference process, and the likelihood of the French Government agreeing to a ceasefire negotiation. On March 6, 1954, Soviet Foreign Minister Molotov received Zhang Wentian, the Chinese Ambassador to the Soviet Union, to discuss China's participation in the Geneva Conference. On March 18, 1954, Deputy Foreign Minister Gromyko met with the French Ambassador to the Soviet Union. Later, on March 29, 1954, Deputy Foreign Minister Kudryavtsev held talks with U.S. Ambassador Bohlen regarding the contents of a U.S. note addressed to the Soviet Union. On March 31, 1954, Molotov again met with Zhang Wentian to discuss several important issues related to the Geneva Conference, including the U.S. position, the timing of the conference, and the representation of Laos and Cambodia (Diep and Thinh, 2024).

Alongside these diplomatic contacts, the Soviet Ministry of Foreign Affairs diligently prepared informational materials and designed the scenario for the Geneva Conference. On March 11, 1954, the Ministry approved a plan to prepare and organize materials in support of the conference. The plan included 18 items concerning the Korean issue, 9 reports and 11 files on the Indochina issue, 7 reports on China, and additional reports and reference materials on Japan. Regarding Indochina, these documents addressed critical subjects such as the political and social positions on peace restoration, U.S. military and economic aid to France, U.S. strategic plans, the British stance, and France's relationship with puppet governments in Vietnam, Laos, and Cambodia. Reference materials also covered U.S. intervention in the Indochina conflict, the British government's position, United Nations documents on Indochina, and French treaty texts with the puppet states. The preparation of these documents was entrusted to various departments within the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (including European Departments I and II, the North America Department, and the Southeast Asia Department) (SRADV, 2019). In parallel, the Ministry also outlined logistical and operational details for the Soviet delegation's participation at the Geneva Conference, from transportation accommodations. On April 7, 1954, the Ministry drafted a list of nine discussion topics for the conference, focusing on key issues related to ending the war and restoring peace in Indochina, such as U.S. intervention, countering claims that China was interfering in Indochina, the Democratic Republic of Vietnam's principles on peace, national unity, independence, and democracy, France's recognition of independence, the withdrawal of foreign troops, and plans for free general elections in Indochina. On the same day, the Presidium of the CPSU Central Committee met and approved a draft directive for the Soviet delegation, instructed the Foreign Ministry to incorporate feedback from the meeting, and authorized consultations with Chinese, Korean, and Vietnamese delegations regarding the directive's key contents. At this point, preparations for the Geneva Conference were complete, and the Soviet delegation was ready to participate actively in the upcoming multilateral conference (SRADV, 2019).

4. THE SOVIET UNION MAINTAINS ITS POSITION AND PERSEVERES IN GENEVA NEGOTIATIONS

On April 26, 1954, the Geneva Conference was officially convened with its first session. On April 27, 1954, the second session - chaired by the Soviet Union - began discussions on Korea and Indochina. When the Indochina issue was raised, France, the United Kingdom, and the United States opposed the participation of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam delegation. As chair of the session, Soviet delegation head Molotov staunchly defended the right of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam to participate as a fully recognized party at the conference, alongside the Soviet Union. He refused to accept the presence of delegations from the Kingdom of Laos, the Kingdom of Cambodia, or the State of Vietnam (Bao Dai) unless the DRV was allowed to attend. The USSR also proposed that the Soviet and British Foreign Ministers co-chair the sessions addressing Indochina. Due to the Soviet Union's firm stance, the major powers - France, the UK, and the U.S. - reluctantly agreed to recognize the DRV's delegate status. Thanks to this unyielding position, on May 4, 1954, the DRV delegation arrived at the Geneva Conference, marking the first time the DRV government participated in a major international peace conference (Van, 2010).

From the outset of the Geneva Conference, the Soviet Union, beyond its role as session chair, engaged in multiple bilateral contacts concerning the Indochina issue. On April 28, 1954, Molotov met with French Foreign Minister Georges Bidault. On May 4, 1954, the Soviet Deputy Foreign Minister met with British Labour MPs to discuss Indochina. These meetings allowed the USSR to gather intelligence, express its positions, and counter efforts to delay the conference. In the April 28 meeting, when Bidault remarked that "it is difficult to negotiate while fighting continues," Molotov promptly retorted that such concerns were mere excuses to delay the Geneva peace talks and argued that Bidault's proposal misinterpreted the Berlin communiqué (SRADV, 2019).

With the ultimate goal of preventing the Indochina War from escalating regionally or globally, the Soviet Union employed both overt and covert diplomatic channels. Publicly, the USSR engaged in direct negotiations on issues such as the participation of Pathet Lao and Khmer Democratic delegations, the Indochina situation, and conditions for peace. The Soviet Union firmly opposed the establishment of military alliances in Indochina and supported the right to political self-determination. In all official and behind-the-scenes meetings, the Soviet delegation consistently upheld the principle that "the first step in restoring peace in Indochina is for all combatant forces to cease fire simultaneously throughout the region, as outlined in the Berlin communiqué" (Diep, 2025). In the covert diplomatic arena, the Soviet Union sought every possible means to engage with military advisors and experts from the delegations of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam and the People's Republic of China to discuss solutions regarding the partition of Vietnam, military disarmament,

and the establishment of a ceasefire monitoring commission. Each issue was examined to define minimum conditions for a viable solution, which would serve as the foundation for negotiation positions at the Conference. The matter of territorial demarcation, in particular, became the subject of intense negotiation. China proposed a solution involving the unification of North and Central Vietnam into a single bloc in exchange for territories of equivalent size in those same regions, outlining three tiers of demarcation: (1) the territory north of the 16th parallel would fall under our control—although this option was deemed unlikely to be feasible; (2) if the first was not accepted, Haiphong would be designated as a free port, allowing France to station a limited number of troops; (3) if this too failed, Route 5, Hanoi, and Haiphong would be designated as a jointly administered and demilitarized zone. Faced with this situation, the Soviet Union maintained the position that "everything would depend on the attitude of the French Government, and also on the position of the U.S. Government, as well as the recognition by all conference delegates of the necessity to resolve the Indochina issue" (Molotov, 1955). Confronted with significant pressure from France, the United Kingdom, the United States, and even concessions made by China, the Soviet Union remained resolute in its stance that "military representatives must further discuss these matters in all their details." Subsequently, the Soviet Union organized a meeting between its military advisors and those of the French delegation at the Geneva Conference to deliberate on the demarcation line in Vietnam, the designation of military regrouping zones in Laos, and the regulations for the withdrawal of military forces from the Red River Delta in Northern Vietnam (SRADV, 2019).

On the issue of national elections to unify Vietnam, complexities arose as the involved parties held divergent views. Although a political declaration had acknowledged that "the resolution of Vietnam's political question shall be based on the principles of independence, unity, and territorial integrity; that the Vietnamese people shall be guaranteed fundamental freedoms by democratic institutions; and that such institutions shall be formed through free elections conducted by secret ballot under supervision as stipulated in the agreement," the United Kingdom, France, and the United States consistently delayed the electoral process and were generally unwilling to commit to national elections in Vietnam. The French delegation in particular repeatedly postponed submitting election-related drafts and extended the timeline for organizing elections. When delays were no longer tenable, France adopted the position of "merely affirming a general principle, leaving the precise date of elections to be determined at a later time" (SRADV, 2019). With a proactive and constructive spirit, the Soviet Union consistently pressed for the discussion of a concrete timeline for general elections. By July 16, 1954, the delegations of the Soviet Union, the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, and the People's Republic of China had reached a consensus on the necessity of setting a date for the

nationwide elections. On July 19, they agreed that general elections to reunify Vietnam would be held two years after the cessation of hostilities.

5. CONCLUSION

As a major power, the Soviet Union not only initiated but also played a pivotal role in resolving the Indochina conflict through the 1954 Geneva International Conference. Employing diverse diplomatic approaches - both public and clandestine, both firm and flexible - the USSR decisively shaped the structure of the negotiations: the principles, methods, content, and scenarios. As a representative of the global forces of peace and progress, the Soviet Union stood shoulder to shoulder with the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, the Pathet Lao Liberation Front, and the Khmer Issarak Democratic Front. It steadfastly advocated for a comprehensive political and military solution in Indochina, with key preconditions including a ceasefire, withdrawal of foreign troops, restoration of peace, and the assurance of independence, unity, and territorial integrity for Vietnam, Laos, and Cambodia - ultimately leading to the end of French colonial rule in Indochina. On July 20, 1954, three ceasefire agreements were signed for Vietnam, Laos, and Cambodia. On July 21, the conference concluded with the adoption of a Joint Declaration encompassing key provisions such as the cessation of hostilities, maintenance and consolidation of peace, consultation for nationwide elections to reunify the country after two years, and enforcement guidelines applicable across all of Indochina. The Geneva Accords marked a major victory for the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, with the Soviet Union playing a decisive role.

With the success of the Geneva Conference, the Soviet Union emerged as a reliable ally not only of Vietnam and the other Indochinese nations, but also as a critical pillar of the global anti-colonial movement. Under Soviet leadership at Geneva, the international standing of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam and the People's Republic of China was significantly elevated. This was a politically significant achievement, particularly as neither the DRV nor the PRC were members of the United Nations at the time. For the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, standing alongside the Soviet Union at an international forum of such historic magnitude brought not only concrete diplomatic successes but also invaluable lessons in diplomacy - forming a crucial foundation for the development of Vietnam's foreign affairs strategy during the resistance war against the United States (1954–1975).

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